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Counting the pieces: a quantitative approach to cultural changes from Roman Karales (Sardinia, Italy)

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Abstract: A single urban excavation can't allow understand the evolution of an ancient city because of its usual small extension. Alas, a good way to get all the data from a small-scale dig is to analyse and understand archaeological finds from different perspectives. An interesting approach to understand trade and cultural changes can be found in quantitative analysis. Accounting archaeological finds can be made in many ways but a common method is to calculate the percentage of MNI of pottery sherds per decades to trace trend graphics. Peaks and lows tell a lot about commercial trade but also changes related to cultural phenomena. The aim of the paper is the comparison of the results about amphorae and fine-ware sherds – both local and imported –, to trace historical-political shifting and to verify how cultural changes influence, or get influenced by, in Sardinia in the moment of transition between Punic and Roman phases.

Keywords: quantitative approach, cultural changes, urban excavation, Cagliari, Sardinia – Italy.

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The ancient city of Karales¹ in the south coast of Sardinia has always been an important harbour in the Mediterranean context, mostly linked with the near cities of African provinces (fig. 1). From the Punic town to the Roman municipium several changes can be listed in urbanistic, cultural and commercial aspects². All these features find their picture in an urban excavation made in 2014 by Anna Luisa Sanna who dug a site located not far from the suggested *forum* of the city in via Caprera 8 (fig. 2). The archaeological material of this excavation has been the object of a recently published work³. This context presents a massive interest in the urbanistic studies of the ancient city of Karales for its position very close to the Roman

¹ The city of Karales was known as KRLY during the Punic period. See Stiglitz 2017. In the Roman phase the centre was identified both as Karalis/Karales and Caralis/Carales. Raimondo Zucca has tried to hypothesize that the plural forms – Karales/Carales – saw their origin in the fusion of the two cities that were, so far, the Punic and civis Romanus communities. See ZUCCA 1999, p. 33; PORRÀ 2008, pp. 48-50.

² COLAVITTI 2003; PIETRA 2018; PIETRA 2019. See also COLAVITTI 1994, pp. 1032-1034 in which the scholar hypothesized a regular urbanistic plan projected in the republican phase that seems to be confirmed by the orientation of the site of via Caprera 8 (NW-SE). From an administrative perspective see PORRÀ 2008.

³ D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019. I would like to thank my colleagues for having given me the opportunity to use their work to try this analysis.

Forum of the Municipium usually located in the modern Piazza del Carmine not far from the theatre-temple of via Malta (fig. 2, G, H)⁴.

1. THE CONTEXT OF VIA CAPRERA

The site of via Caprera 8 (fig. 3), seems to enlighten more details in the urbanistic plan of this portion of the city⁵ from the Roman Republican until Late Antiquity. The site consists in several buildings erected one upon the other creating a complex stratigraphy in which phases of abandonment and reuse has allowed the creation of various 'garbage layers' useful, in our perspective, to define some commercial features of the ancient Karales analysing them from a quantitative perspective (fig. 4). The excavation led to the identification of 8 phases indicated by Latin letters from A to H. The most ancient phase – phase A – consisted in some little evidences found below the floor US 74 with no material culture in association⁶. Then, it was created a first rectangular building dated in a moment before the 1st century BC for the presence of a *titulo picto* made upon the shoulder of a Dressel 2-4 *amphora*⁷. After the first half of the 1st century AD, in the phase C, was erected a new building along a first lifting of the walking surface of the room⁸; the structure cannot be surely linked with the previous one, even if it follows the same orientation and dimensions. After the abandonment of this building⁹, in the first imperial age is documented a second lifting of the

⁴ PIETRA 2019.

⁵ M. Giuman in GIUMAN, MARTORELLI 2019, pp. 718-722.

⁶ SANNA 2019, p. 5.

⁷ SANNA 2019, pp. 5-6. For the *titulo picto* and for the amphora see respectively FARRE 2019, pp. 661-662 fig. 3; A. Pontis in PONTIS, D'ORLANDO 2019, pp. 209-210.

⁸ SANNA 2019, pp. 6-8.

⁹ SANNA 2019, pp. 8-10.

floor with a powerful layer that has been levelled to create a plain surface on which is possible to hypothesize the creation of an open-air 'campanian-manner garden'¹⁰ realised reusing some thin-walled vases¹¹ and some imitations¹², a late-republican cooking pot¹³ and a halved Dressel 2-4 amphora¹⁴ settled along the walls. This garden was in use until the 2nd century AD¹⁵. Once again, the site was filled up with pottery and other discharge material and then object of spoliation phenomena. In the late 7th century AD the structure was probably definitively abandoned before the reuse of the site in medieval and post-medieval times which has surely compromised the most recent phases of the area¹⁶.

2. THE METODOLOGY

The site has seen the integral study and publication of the archaeological material¹⁷ that has allowed to give attention to the whole record, including residual findings, here used as a powerful informative tool. Also, the massive presence of residual findings felt as an issue concerning stratigraphical analysis, if properly interpreted could give us a number of interesting hints about commercial routes and material culture changes in a diachronic perspective. In this paper I would try to use a quantitative method that allows to verify tendencies in trades, trying in the same time to validate its use for the study of cultural changes phenomenon.

¹⁰ PARODO 2019. See also Ciro Parodo in this volume.

¹¹ NAPOLITANO 2019, pp. 77-78 tav I.

¹² L. Pinelli in PINELLI, PINELLI 2019, p. 352 tav. V, figg. 12-13.

¹³ PINELLI 2019, p. 411 tav. I, fig. 2.

¹⁴ D'ORLANDO 2019, pp. 191-192 tav. V, fig. 5; FARRE 2019, p. 660, figg. 1a-b.

¹⁵ SANNA 2019, pp. 10-11.

¹⁶ SANNA 2019, pp. 11-14.

¹⁷ D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019.

This analysis takes its starting point from the method '*media ponderata per decennio*'¹⁸ exposed by Nicola Terrenato and Giovanni Ricci in 1998 for residual finds of Palatino excavation in Rome¹⁹, used before that moment by Elizabeth Fentress for African red slip ware but there indicated as 'even percentage per year'²⁰. The methodology I choose for this analysis sees its main difference in the use of the minimum number of individuals instead of the simple number of fragments. The MNI of a certain pottery class has been distinguished by autoptic analysis of every single fragment. The methodology consists in taking the minimum number of individuals of a certain form of a pottery production and then dividing this number for its date range of utilisation²¹ and then setting this computation for decades. Paraphrasing the words of Nicola Terrenato e Giovanni Ricci, the method requires to take the total amount of fragments with a same chronology (here the MNI with same chronology) and dividing it for the entire period of its production and then assigning the resulting ratio in the entire time frame. If we have 14 fragments dated from 30 to 130 AD, we must divide the total

¹⁸ TERRENATO, RICCI 1998. Same methodology in FENTRESS, PERKINS 1988; CECI 2003; FENTRESS *et alii* 2004; CECI, SANTANGELI VALENZANI 2016, pp. 74-75. See also FURLAN 2019, pp. 47-71.

¹⁹ This computation has seen a renewed flourishing in recent years Sardinian archaeology. See TRONCHETTI 2003, fig. 6; FALEZZA 2009a; FALEZZA 2009b; FALEZZA 2009c; TRONCHETTI 2014a; PONTIS 2019b (already used in a non-published study of the African red-slip ware of the so-called 'vano A' of the southern block in the former military area in Nora excavated by the University of Cagliari; see PONTIS 2018); BOLZONI *et alii* 2020. A different method of computation was adopted by Andrea Roppa (based on a 25 years scale instead of 10 as in '*media ponderata*' of Terrenato and Ricci. See ROPPA 2013, pp. 105-107.

²⁰ FENTRESS, PERKINS 1988; FENTRESS *et alii* 2004.

²¹ A simpler process – even percentage per centuries – has been used by Monica Ceci to verify the enormous number of pottery sherds collected in the *Imperial Fora* context in Rome dividing the entire number of fragments of a pottery class for its overall period of use (i.e., black-glazed number of pottery fragments were divided for 3 centuries). CECI 2003; CECI, SANTANGELI VALENZANI 2016, pp. 74-89.

(14) for the entire period of production (100 years), giving for every here the related ratio (14:100=0,14). In the end we add the entire ratios of every production analysed to obtain a trustful trend of the chronological distribution of the material culture of the context²². This methodology was adopted for every sherd of *amphorae* and fine pottery for which it was possible to identify a specific form or, at least, a production that allows a trustful chronological framework for the entire analysis (tabs. 1, 3-4, 7-8, 10).

In this computation I would like to consider whole imports starting from fine pottery to *amphorae*, excluding in this phase terracotta lamps and glass objects for which it is not always sure the production site. Archaeological materials date back from 5th century BC to 7th century CE. Fine pottery comprehends black-glazed ware of Campanian production and regional/local manufacture²³, Italic sigillata²⁴, African red slip ware²⁵ and Thin-walled pottery of Italic and Hispanic provenance²⁶. The site document a great number of commercial amphorae sherds of Punic²⁷, Italic²⁸, Hispanic²⁹ and African³⁰ production along a small number of specimens from Gallia and the eastern Mediterranean³¹. On 8575 amphorae fragments only 424 could be identified clearly while 164 were at least indicated for the area of production and their dating range (tab. 2). It seems clear that a sharp change from one area of imports to another can easily be noted using this

²² TERRANATO, RICCI 1998, pp. 92-93.

²³ LOI 2019a.

²⁴ ANEDDA 2019.

²⁵ PONTIS 2019a.

²⁶ NAPOLITANO 2019.

²⁷ LOI 2019b.

²⁸ D'ORLANDO 2019.

²⁹ PONTIS, D'ORLANDO 2019.

³⁰ SORO 2019a.

³¹ SORO 2019b.

method, but the question is if we can use this method to analyse even cultural changes, usually slower than those of the markets, and what information this analysis can give us to understand the material culture of the past.

3. ROMANIZATION IN SARDINIA AND MATERIAL CULTURE CHANGE

The process of cultural change after the Roman conquest of the *Provincia Sardinia* was slow and with results somehow very different from those of the rest of the territories of the empire. Very few are the colonies deducted in the Island³² and apparently, only the cities on the coast seem to have received some kind of *décor urbanus*³³, while rural areas could have been left apart from Rome attention at least for the first centuries of roman dominance³⁴. In the historiographical debate about Roman Sardinia, the conquest of the Island has two different phases, the first after the II Punic war with the creation of the *Provincia Sardinia et Corsica* and a second try in the II century BC, contemporary with the III punic War in the so-called 'second conquest of the Island'³⁵. In this phase is possible to notice a stronger interest of Rome for the Island along some important facts as the creation of a Forma Sardinia dedicated by T. Sempronius Gracchus senior in the temple of Mater Matuta in Rome after a battle won against the

³² Colonia Iulia Turris Libisonis deducted in the second half of the 1st century BC in the north-western part of the Island (MASTINO 2001, p. 788 nota 24) and Colonia Iulia Augusta Uselis for which it is not already possible to state a deduction or a promotion to date in the first half of the 1st century AD (MASTINO, ZUCCA 2011, p. 456; PORRÀ 2012).

³³ ZUCCA 1994; GHIOTTO 2004.

³⁴ This could be identified as a bias due to our little number of excavations in rural sites of the Late-republican phases. In this period is possible to focus on a series of farms (see notes 68-71), and a few necropolises (PUDDU 2019) and settlements (ROPPA 2013).

³⁵ IBBA 2015, pp. 19-25.

Sardinians³⁶. A third moment of cultural push by Rome is the Augustan age, after a deep administrative reform to contain the 'barbarians' *populations* of Sardinia³⁷.

Those moments are clearly highlighted by the volume of imported goods, our main factor of cultural influence from a population to another. This perspective takes place from the idea that material culture is one of the main aspects that identifies a population. For this reason, if material culture changes there could have been some deep modifications in the self-conception of a population. This idea has been strongly debated and tested in recent years through a great number of different contexts³⁸. An interesting point about this issue comes from a paper by Mark Grahame in which the scholar, according to Pierre Bourdieu's theory, states³⁹: «if individuals are brought up in differing social and physical environments, their vision of the world will also differ. *Identity* becomes implicated because different visions of the world form the basis for the *construction* of gender, class, ethnic and other social differences. If the *material world* is so integral to the *constitution of identity* then a change to the material world must imply a change to the *social practices through which identities are created*»⁴⁰. But what is the evidence of the process of acquisition of Roman customs? What marks this phenomenon in Sardinia? The main questions to try to solve this problem

³⁶ Liv. 41 28, 8-10.

³⁷ CORDA, IBBA 2018.

³⁸ BATS 1994; ROTH 2003; DIETLER 2010; DIETLER 2015. In Sardinia see also PUDDU 2019; BOLZONI *et alii* 2020, p. 84 note 49. In a general perspective see GRAHAME 1998; TERRENATO 1998 and for identities issues of romanization ROTH, KELLER 2007; VAN DOMMELEN, TERRENATO 2007; VAN DOMMELEN, KNAPP 2010.

³⁹ GRAHAME 1998, pp. 3-4.

⁴⁰ Italics by the author.

are: is material culture a reliable medium to understand cultural changes?
Is this type of quantitative analysis useful in this type of studies?

4. ACCOUNTING MATERIAL CULTURE FOR THE STUDY OF ROMANIZATION PROCESSES

In this section I would try to expose the results of the analysis, focusing only in a second moment on the material culture of the moment of transition from the Punic to the Roman dominion of the Island to better fit the conference topic. For this reason, I would try to devote the next section on the so-called family of the black-glazed pottery and its regional/local imitation and then a focus on the economic and commercial aspects. First of all, analysing the general trend of imports based on the archaeological material found in via Caprera 8 using the methodology just explained (tab. 1), we can easily identify four capital moments of interest: the first is a strong increase of imports after the proclamation of the *Provincia Sardinia et Corsica* that saw its peak in the years of the III Punic war, a moment of strong reorganization in Roman Sardinia, a moment known as we have already seen as 'the second conquest of the Island'. Then there is a deep low in the first times of 1st century BC, probably due to the weakening of sea trade during the social war. After the civil war we see another strong phase of imports that we can date to Augustan age that decreases progressively in the late 1st century AD, after this moment almost all the imported goods apparently come from African provinces. The peaks in the Late Republican phases of via Caprera could have been however a reflection of some more powerful layers dated to this period, aspect that we have to keep in mind

analysing those data⁴¹. At first, I am going to analyse separately amphorae trade and fine pottery markets thinking of them as two different information sources. The first mostly linked to commercial routes and trade interests, freer from cultural aspects than the second⁴², more influenced by trends and people preferences⁴³.

Concerning *amphorae* and their presence (tab. 3), is perceivable a strong presence of Punic amphorae made in Sardinia all along the 2nd century BC, a moment of strong productivity for the Island. At the same time, we see a shift from African-Punic imports to Italic goods after the Augustan age when the first seems almost disappear until the late I century AD when the former leave the place to African Imperial imports. If we focus on the area of production (tab. 4), considering together Punic and Imperial age African amphorae we can see a clear moment of crisis of African imports that is contemporary with a similar phenomenon for Sardinian amphorae and an increase of Italic imports that has its top in the second half of the 1st century BC. It is already interesting to see that the last moment of a flourishing trade for Sardinian and African goods in late republican age falls in the period of the Social War, a moment of exporting difficulties for the Italic harbours and producers. Emphasizing this data on a cultural issue, it can be seen a dominant position of Punic goods just until Augustan Age, the first moment in which italic goods seems to arrive at the same volume of Punic ones⁴⁴. This aspect remarks a deep link with the previous cultural

⁴¹ From this point of view, it could be very useful to analyse other pottery assemblages from different contexts of the city of Karales to verify those tendencies.

⁴² Some scholars doubt about the cultural marker value of any type of pottery, in particular amphorae. See HAEUSSLER 2016, pp. 22-23. For a 'relative' value of pottery information to understand cultural changes see TERRENATO 1998.

⁴³ HAEUSSLER 2016, pp. 109-110.

⁴⁴ LOI 2019b. To separate Punic and 'Roman' tradition amphorae is a difficult task and surely not one of the aims of this paper. About this cultural issue Martin-Kilcher wrote that the type Carthage

customs and the traditional commercial routes hard to be forgotten in the Island. The deep link between Sardinia and Punic culture is perceivable even from some contexts of the Terme Centrali and Case a Mare of Nora where material culture is already Punic-oriented even in the 1st century AD⁴⁵.

Very different is what can be seen analysing only imported fine pottery. On a total amount of 1799 fragments only 1310 were identified as diagnostic elements (72,8%). Considering the entire fine-ware assemblage is possible to recognise a great number of Thin-walled fragments (801; 45%) followed by a fair amount of the entire family of Black-glazed pottery (579; 32%) (tab. 5). The percentage of diagnostic Thin-walled fragments (778 on 801; 97,2 %) corresponds to a very small number of specimens (57), hinting a very low breaking point. Very different is what is possible to state about Black-glazed pottery for which are counted a small number of diagnostic sherds (114 on 579; 19,2 %) with a sensitive presence of Sardinian Black-glazed gray paste production (73 against 41 Campanian fragments). Putting this data in an even percentage per decade computation we could clearly see a peak of imports for Campanian ware in the first half of the 2nd century BC, just before the so-called “second conquest of the Island” and a strong production increase of Sardinian Black-glazed gray paste ware (end of 2nd-beginning of 1st century BC) in the years of the Social war followed by a

Early type 4 is the ‘romanised’ version of the Punic Maña C2 amphora. See MARTIN-KILCHER 1999. For some Sardinian productions that has been identified by the Facem group see facem.at.

⁴⁵ The first is the context Td14927 of the “Terme Centrali” where in the I century BC Punic and Roman material culture are almost paired (49% vs 51%). Even more Punic oriented are Ti 14959 of the “Terme Centrali” where this ratio is even more Punic-oriented (69% vs 31) and Aa 31856 of the “Case a mare” (59% vs 41). Cfr. BOLZONI *et alii* 2020, pp. 83-88.

peak for Italic red slip ware in the late 1st century BC, a moment that is possible to pair with the Augustan Age (tab. 6).

Thinking about fine pottery as guide fossils of contacts and cultural interaction, is possible to identify four main areas of producers representing Italic, Hispanic, African markets along the Sardinian manufacturers (tabs. 7-8). Italic production has its two peaks in the moments of greatest interest of Rome for the Island contemporary with the 'second conquest of the Island' and then in the late 1st century BC. For this reason, it is possible to argue that second conquest of the Island could probably be interpreted as a far more important moment than a simple strategy of political and administrative reorganization of the land. We can even suggest to see in this phase the very first try of Rome to make the Island more 'Roman'. This phenomenon seems to have been stopped a first time in the first decades of the 1st century BC when the Social war and the improved role of Sardinia as the granary of Rome may have changed the future prospects of the Island⁴⁶. In this very moment is important to point out that from a quantitative perspective is possible to hypothesize the substitution of Campanian pottery by its homologues made by Sardinian producers, which presence seems to continue and prosper throughout the Civil war and the Augustan peace.

⁴⁶ Late republican age is a phase of deep changings in whole administrative and economic features for the roman government that sees a shifting from personal to massive landowners as the extreme consequences of what the Gracchus brothers tried to stop in the II century BC. For this reason, it is not excluded that what is proposed here as an effect of a politic change (i.e. the Annona role of Sardinia) could have been already one of the causes of the new administrative and cultural choices. A great modification could be documented in the *ager olbiensis* where Nero create a large property to his lover Claudia Atte. See PIETRA 2013, p. 251.

5. MATERIAL CULTURE CHANGES IN MOMENTS OF TRANSITION: BLACK-GLAZED PRODUCTIONS IN SARDINIA

The use of Sardinian Black-glazed gray paste ware widespread in the rural sites of the Island is one of the strongest signs of the diffusion of this external custom in Sardinia that makes clear a cultural change in the situation of the inland⁴⁷. From a commercial perspective is interesting to focus on a cross-reference between the situation of Nora and Cagliari (via Caprera 8). If we focus on the analysis made by Giovanna Falezza concerning the Roman Black-glazed pottery of the *forum* of the *Municipium Norense*, we could see a similar tendency for whole Italic production and a peak for Sardinian in the very first years of the 1st century BC (tabs. 7, 9)⁴⁸. In comparison with the context of Cagliari this last phenomenon seems to be less evident although a similarity can be argued about a phase in which this pottery class was far more common in the Sardinian markets. Another aspect is the difference between the amount of Sardinian Black-glazed ware in the context of Nora and via Caprera 8. In the former is relevant a stronger presence of this pottery class in the whole 1st century BC and 1st century AD more similar to the ratio always stated by Carlo Tronchetti who wrote about a sensitive higher presence of Sardinian Black-glazed gray paste⁴⁹ as in many other contexts⁵⁰. In fact, the context of Karales testify a massive

⁴⁷ A comprehensive study of the production of black-glazed gray paste ware is still far from being achieved. A first reorganization of our knowledge in TRONCHETTI 1996a, pp. 32-33; TRONCHETTI 1996b. For a recent study of a rural context see DE LUCA 2017. In a more general perspective see the paper from Carlo Tronchetti and Gianna De Luca in this volume.

⁴⁸ FALEZZA 2009a, pp. 644-645 fig. 12.

⁴⁹ TRONCHETTI 2018, p. 14.

⁵⁰ See Nora contexts of Piccole Terme (COSENTINO 2018, pp. 33-38 fig. 1) or "Ex area militare" (DE LUCA 2018, pp. 41-47 fig. 1).

presence of Sardinian black-glazed gray paste ware which has a powerful increase of production just in the end of the 2nd century BC, long before the peak detected by Giovanna Falezza about the same pottery coming from Nora Roman *forum*⁵¹. A very personal and therefore open to discussion explication for this difference can be seen in the unlike relationship between the centre and their hinterlands, a diverse preference between imported and local fine-ware and mainly a different relationship between producing and consuming areas. If the two first aspects are problematic, for the latter element there are already very poor data concerning local pottery *atelier* and purely hypothetical is the reconstruction of the internal market of fine-ware trade. A possible local production has been associated by Carlo Tronchetti to the so-called 'Cagliari 1' ware dated from the 3rd to the beginning of the 2nd century BC, related to the Punic imitations of the Attic prototypes but already strongly affected by centro-italic influences as proved by decorative and formal features⁵². Very rare is the presence of *ateliers* context linked with kilns which in Southern Sardinia are attested in San Sperate⁵³ – located in the hinterland of Karales –, Masainas⁵⁴ and others two both in Trexenta in the village of Sant'Andrea Frius⁵⁵ and Sisini (Senorbì) from an unpublished site in which is possible to document a feasible pottery furnace associated

⁵¹ FALEZZA 2009a, pp. 644-645 fig. 12. A similar ratio is attested from the Case al Mare and Terme Centrali contexts (Aa 31856 and Ti 14959) where imported Black-glazed pottery document and higher presence than local productions. Cfr. BOLZONI *et alii* 2020, p. 86-88 fig. 8.

⁵² First a *rosetta* decoration in the bottom of L. 22 derived cups and the shape of L. 27 cup, both from the centro-italic *Ateliers des petites estampilles*. See TRONCHETTI 2001, p. 277. For a more recent analysis see TRONCHETTI 2018.

⁵³ UGAS 1993, pp. 39-41.

⁵⁴ TRONCHETTI 1998, pp. 373-375.

⁵⁵ SPANO 1874, p. 77; ROWLAND 1981, p. 107. The furnace of Sant'Andrea Frius was found below the municipal building of the village and immediately destroyed making impossible to define the associated pottery production.

with a great number of gray paste ware fragments⁵⁶. Those elements are little hints of a dispersed and peripheral production centres of local fine wares which could to be located far from the main cities of the coast⁵⁷. Specimens of the so-called Punic Black-glazed pottery⁵⁸ have been documented in a very large area consisting in the immediate surroundings of Karales and the near region of Trexenta, specifically in the necropolis of S. Lucia of Gesico⁵⁹ and Senorbì⁶⁰, along some centres of the Campidano plain nearer to Cagliari like Serramanna and Assemini⁶¹. The even more sensitive diffusion of gray paste ware in those areas explain how much widespread could have been this production. The presence of Punic black glazed pottery in those sites of the rural hinterland of Cagliari and then of the Late Republican phase Sardinian black-glazed gray paste ware⁶²

⁵⁶ Unpublished site in study by the author. A first communication of this context was made by the author in the 4th Iarpothp Conference in Athens (November 2019) in a lecture entitled '*From Urban to rural: trade and production between Caralis and its hinterland (Sardinia, Italy)*' which is going to published in the proceedings of the conference.

⁵⁷ *Contra* Tronchetti 2018, p. 12. In this paper Carlo Tronchetti states that in the Island coexist different ateliers surely located in the main urban centres: «Nell'isola coesistono diverse Officine dislocate sicuramente quantomeno nei centri urbani principali, ma la carenza di ritrovamenti degli stabilimenti produttivi inficia notevolmente le ipotesi ricostruttive dei processi di produzione». For a general perspective of the relationship between Karales and its hinterland see TRONCHETTI 2004.

⁵⁸ ACQUARO *et alii* 2002; AMADORI *et alii* 2004; DEL VAIS 2007; TRONCHETTI 2008; AMADORI *et alii* 2009; TRONCHETTI 2014b; TRONCHETTI 2018, pp. 12-13; ZAMPARO 2018. See also Carla Del Vais' paper in this volume.

⁵⁹ TRONCHETTI 1996b. S. Lucia of Gesico is a punico-roman necropolis in use from the 3rd century BC to 1st century AD.

⁶⁰ TRONCHETTI 2001, p. 278 note 16.

⁶¹ TRONCHETTI 2001, pp. 278-279. The author does not mention the name of those sites but one could be the punico-roman necropolis of Su Fraigu of Serramanna. See COSSU, GARAU 2003.

⁶² TRONCHETTI 2018, pp. 12-14.

confirms a powerful inner market in the context of the southern part of the Island along a strong continuity from the Punic to the Roman dominion⁶³.

6. SOME ECONOMIC AND COMMERCIAL REMARKS

At last, we can analyse in pair amphorae and fine pottery trade in order to verify if there are any differences in trends during the Late Republican age (tab. 10). It is clear that African imports from the 1st century AD are almost coherent and regular in both amphorae and fine pottery market, a possible sign of a situation of stability in which peaks and lows are just explainable as ups and downs of the request of a particular good. Different is the situation of the last two centuries of the Republic. Very interesting is the difference of Sardinian amphorae presence compared to Sardinian black-glazed ware. In the very moment in which the amphorae trade decreased, Sardinian fine pottery saw its first peak. The contemporary peak of Sardinian fine pottery and the low of Sardinian amphorae suggests an unbalanced situation. While the first sees an increasing request that might have been caused by the contraction of the presence of Campanian black-glazed pottery imports, the second, probably related to agricultural farmer production, saw a big crisis. This last aspect could reflect the decreasing possibility to sell the surplus of their production that could be related with acts of brigandage and administrative reforms echoed in some happenings described by Roman sources⁶⁴. Another element that could

⁶³ Some of those problems could be solved in the future by archaeometric analysis and a vast work of surface survey already activated by the University of Cagliari (Progetto Sub Terris – Ortacesus).

⁶⁴ We know about a series of indigenous revolts after the C. Metellus reforms suppressed only in 92 BC by T. Albucius against what Cicero named 'mastrucati latrunculi'. Cic. *De prov. consul.* 7, 15.

explain this historic landscape is a more onerous role of Sardinia in the Annona system which importance is proved by some extraordinary second tenth exaction occurred in the 2nd century BC and the siege of M. Emilius Lepidus of the Sardinian cities in 78 BC to interrupt the *frumentarium* supply to Rome to create a military advantage⁶⁵.

This last element could have had a possible mirror in the chronology of some of the rural farms excavated in Sardinia. We owe to cite at least, Truncu 'e Molas⁶⁶ and Pauli Stincus⁶⁷ in the western coast, excavated by Peter Van Dommelen *équipe* and the reuse of the nuraghe of Tres Bias in Tinnura⁶⁸ in the north-western coast as long as S'Imbalconadu⁶⁹, not far from Olbia. All these farms have one thing in common, all of them stopped their activities between the second half of the 2nd and the 1st century BC. If we cannot say that every situation can be explained by the same reason, this peculiar coincidence hints the possibility of a bigger project for the rural sites of the Sardinian outback. Can this be a reflection of the changing from the independent management left to the farmers to a more organised and different landowner politics that privileges only big owners despite small farms? As we have tried to explain studying material culture, the first effects of this cultural change started in the beginning of the 1st century BC. At this moment, after the decrease of Campanian black-glazed pottery imports, some Sardinian producer increase their production to fill up the

⁶⁵ PAIS 1999, p. 197.

⁶⁶ See VAN DOMMELEN *et alii* 2008; VAN DOMMELEN *et alii* 2012; The farm of Truncu 'è molas stops its activities in the second half of the 2nd century BC.

⁶⁷ VAN DOMMELEN *et alii* 2006. This complex was abandoned by the end of the 2nd century BC.

⁶⁸ MADAU 1994.

⁶⁹ SANCIU 1997.

request of this kind of good, researched and widespread in almost all roman sites of Sardinia between 1st century BC and 1st century AD⁷⁰.

7. DISCUSSION

In conclusion of this brief analysis is possible to point out some conclusive sentences. At first, we cannot assume that Campanian black-glazed ware is a sign of a process of Romanization in act⁷¹, but is quite interesting how this pottery class was taken as a formal model for regional mass production⁷². About this issue is interesting what Astrid Van Oyen stated writing of the standardization of *terra sigillata* which presents some similarities with Black-glazed productions: «I argued that *terra sigillata*'s standardization was very much historically significant, as it afforded particular kinds of actions, different to other pottery. As a result of their standardization, for example, *terra sigillata* pots could be stacked easily, facilitating long-distance transport on carts and ships, and often arrived on consumption sites in sets. As sets containing many different shapes, *terra sigillata* pots could easily cater for the needs of different types of usage in different contexts. Paradoxically, then, it was precisely their relative homogeneity as a material class that spurred flexible reinterpretation of

⁷⁰ No one has ever tried to analyse the widespread of Sardinian black-glazed gray paste ware in the entire territory of the Island although it has been ever defined widespread or, citing Carlo Tronchetti, "a diffusione capillare" (TRONCHETTI 2015, pp. 1809-1810, 1812; TRONCHETTI 2018). For a recent point of view of this pottery production see Carlo Tronchetti and Gianna De Luca in this volume. See also DE LUCA 2017; 2019.

⁷¹ TERRENATO 1998, p. 27; STEK 2013; HAEUSSLER 2016, pp. 22-23.

⁷² Those ateliers keep producing from the 2nd century BC to the 1st century AD adapting its features to the request of different social classes and evolving its morphology starting from a Campanian *repertoire* and developing its own types, to acquire and elaborate in the last phases some Italic red-slip ware forms. TRONCHETTI 2015, pp. 1809-1810 fig. 1.

terra sigillata pots»⁷³. Is already interesting to specify that communities that felt different needs does not use easily non-traditional pottery shapes as we know from Martin Pitts studies about the Gallo-belgic beakers used to drink beer that persisted along “roman pottery” because the latter would not fit the same function⁷⁴. In this perspective material culture is a relevant proof of cultural changes and refusals. Nonetheless, we have to mark a great difference between cultural integration of life, religious and funeral roman customs and what we can define a shallow take-over of some pottery forms without falling in a strong bias⁷⁵. In fact, in the Sardinian society of the Late Republican age that we can define Punic in almost every cultural aspect, we slowly arrive to identify some significant element of Roman culture only in the 1st century BC. This issue is exaggerated by the few excavations of rural context and our little knowing about many aspects of the traditional material culture evolution of too much areas of the Island. We have already pointed out that the importance of material culture. In this perspective Romanization has seen a never-ending debate but is undoubtable that material culture has a fundamental role for our understanding of a series of phenomena for which interpretation we have only some kinds of ‘negative traces’. From this point of view there are some new theoretical positions quite resourceful for the future. In fact, some post-colonial positions are trying to create a more complex system of interrelations between humanity and things in order to better understand this relationship⁷⁶. Those studies

⁷³ VAN OYEN 2017, p. 297.

⁷⁴ PITTS 2015.

⁷⁵ This is what Nicola Terrenato has remarked writing that “a lot of (*cultural*) indicators may be relevant, but none is diagnostic in isolation”. TERRENATO 1998, p. 27. For a dialogue between material culture and identity see HAEUSSLER 2016.

⁷⁶ VAN OYEN 2013.

are mostly enrolled in the side of identity studies which represent a new approach to those issues that has already given its first interesting results in Sardinian scholarship⁷⁷. In the same way, considering what my analysis has tried to demonstrate, is really possible to give to Sardinian Black-glazed ware a fundamental role in our understanding of the evolution of the cultural processes of Late Republican age in Sardinia. A specific role that must be verified in different areas and other types of sites trying to define if there is a difference in trade tendencies and formal preferences between urban and rural sites and different parts of the Island⁷⁸. Another aspect, omitted here for brevity, is the relationship between Punic tableware and external models such as the finest Attic and Campanian pottery to define if there is a moment when Sardinian people stopped using the first to prefer the second⁷⁹. In this context would be probably useful to keep using quantitative analysis to verify if there is a key moment in this process.

⁷⁷ VAN DOMMELEN 2007; PUDDU 2019.

⁷⁸ This kind of analysis has been presented by the writer in the 4th Iarpothp Conference in Athens (November 2019) in a lecture entitled '*From Urban to rural: trade and production between Caralis and its hinterland (Sardinia, Italy)*' which is going to be published in the proceedings of the conference.

⁷⁹ Some interesting point about this issue in BOLZONI *et alii* 2020.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

AMADORI *et alii* 2004: M.L. Amadori, C. Del Vais, B. Fabbri, S. Lanza, *La ceramica punica a vernice nera da Tharros (Cabras – Oristano): le letture storiche e indagini archeometriche*, in F. Berti, B. Fabbri, S. Gualtieri, C. Guarnieri (eds.), *Metodologia di ricerca e obiettivi degli studi: lo stato dell'arte - Atti della 6° Giornata di Archeometria della ceramica (Ferrara, 9 aprile 2002)*, Bologna 2004, pp. 39-58.

AMADORI *et alii* 2009: M.L. Amadori, C. Del Vais, G. Raffaelli, *Indagini archeometriche sulla ceramica punica a vernice nera dall'ex Mercato di Olbia*, in *Le classi ceramiche. Situazione degli studi – Atti della 10° giornata di Archeometria della ceramica (Roma 5-7 aprile 2006)*, Bari 2009, pp. 111-120.

ANEDDA 2019: A. Anedda, *La sigillata italica e sud-gallica*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 111-138, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

BATS 1994: M. Bats, *La vaisselle culinaire comme marker culturel: l'exemple de la Gaule méridionale et de la Grande-Grèce (Ive-Ier s. av. J.-C.)*, in *Terre cuite et société. Actes des XIVe rencontres internationales d'archéologie et d'histoire d'Antibes (1993)*, Juan-les-Pins 1994, pp. 407-424.

BOLZONI *et alii* 2020: G. Bolzoni, I. Frontori, S. Mevio, *Nora, III secolo a.C. – I secolo a.C.: contesti e materiali dall'area E*, in J. Bonetto, R. Carboni, M. Giuman, A. Zara (ed.), *Nora Antiqua II. Nora dalla costituzione della Provincia all'età augustea. Atti del Convegno di Studi (Pula 5-6 ottobre 2018)*, Roma 2020, pp. 77-93.

BONETTO *et alii* 2009: J. Bonetto, G. Falezza, A.R. Ghiotto (eds.), *Nora. Il foro romano storia di un'area urbana dall'età fenicia alla tarda antichità 1997-2006. Volume II.2. I materiali romani e gli altri reperti*, Padova 2009.

CECI 2013: M. Ceci, *Fori Imperiali: la storia di un paesaggio urbano attraverso i contesti ceramici*, in M. Ceci (ed.), *Contesti ceramici dai Fori Imperiali*, Oxford 2013, pp. 1-9.

CECI, SANTANGELI VALENZANI 2016: M. Ceci, R. Santangeli Valenzani, *La ceramica nello scavo archeologico*, Roma 2016.

COLAVITTI 1994: A.M. Colavitti, *Ipotesi sulla struttura urbanistica di Carales romana*, in A. Mastino, P. Ruggeri (eds.), *L'Africa romana (Atti del X convegno di studio, Oristano 11-13 dicembre 1992)*, Sassari 1994, pp. 1021-1034.

COLAVITTI 2003: A.M. Colavitti, *Cagliari: forma e urbanistica*, Roma 2003.

CORDA, IBBA 2018: A.M. Corda, A. Ibba, *Militavit in Sardinia: aggiornamenti (1990-2016)*, in S. Magnani (ed.), *Domi Forisque. Omaggio a Giovanni Brizzi*, Bologna 2018, pp. 83-97.

COSENTINO 2018: V. Cosentino, *Problemi di ceramica a vernice nera dalle Piccole Terme di Nora. Residualità, importazioni e produzioni locali*, in GIANNATTASIO 2018, pp. 33-39.

COSSU, GARAU 2003: C. Cossu, E. Garau, *La necropoli: Tra Cartaginesi e Romani. Lo scavo della necropoli di Serramanna (CA)*, in *Quaderni del Museo* 1, pp. 11-18.

DE LUCA 2017: G. De Luca, *Ceramiche a vernice nera da Su Landiri Durci (CI) tra produzioni locali e importazioni*, in *Layers. Archeologia Territorio Contesti* 2, pp. 73-113, <https://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/2924>.

DE LUCA 2018: G. De Luca, *Ceramiche a vernice nera dall'ex area militare di Nora. Qualche riflessione sulla produzione a pasta grigia*, in GIANNATTASIO 2018, pp. 41-49.

DE LUCA 2019: G. De Luca, *Rotte e mercati marittimi nella Sardegna meridionale di età romana: la ceramica a vernice nera come marker sociale e culturale*, in MARTORELLI 2019, pp. 251-260.

DEL VAIS 2007: C. Del Vais, *Nuove ricerche sulla ceramica punica a vernice nera*, in S. Angiolillo, M. Giuman, A. Pasolini (eds.), *Ricerca e confronti. Giornate di studio di archeologia e storia dell'arte*, Cagliari 2007, pp. 171-182.

DIETLER 2010: M. Dietler, *Archaeologies of Colonialism: Consumption, Entanglement and Violence in Ancient Mediterranean France*, Berkeley 2010.

DIETLER 2015: M. Dietler, *Rencontres culinaires: la culture matérielle incorporée*, in R. Roure (ed.), *Contacts et acculturations en Méditerranée occidentale*.

Hommages à Michel Bats (Actes du colloque de Hyères, 15-18 septembre 2011), Arles/Aix-en-Provence 2015, pp. 153-159.

D'ORLANDO 2019: D. D'Orlando, *Contenitori anforici di produzione italica*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 187-205, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

D. D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019: D. D'Orlando, F. Doria, L. Soro (eds.), *Archeologia urbana a Cagliari. Scavi in via Caprera 8 (2014-2015)*, Cagliari 2019.

FALEZZA 2009a: G. Falezza, *La ceramica romana a vernice nera*, in Bonetto *et alii* 2009, pp. 621-645.

FALEZZA 2009b: G. Falezza, *La ceramica sigillata africana*, in BONETTO *et alii* 2009, pp. 665-679.

FALEZZA 2009c: G. Falezza, *La ceramica africana da cucina*, in BONETTO *et alii* 2009, pp. 681-691.

FARRE 2019: C. Farre, *La documentazione epigrafica*, in D'Orlando *et alii* 2019, pp. 659-668, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

FENTRESS, PERKINS 1988: E. Fentress, P. Perkins, *Counting African Red Slip Ware*, in A. Mastino (ed.), *L'Africa romana (Atti del V convegno di studio, Sassari 11-13 dicembre 1987)*, Sassari 1988, pp. 205-218.

FENTRESS *et alii* 2004: E. Fentress, S. Fontana, R.B. Hitchner, P. Perkins, *Accounting for ARS: Fineware and Sites in Sicily and Africa*, in S.E. Alcock, J.F. Cherry (eds.) *Side-by-side survey: comparative regional studies in the Mediterranean world*, Oxford 2004, pp. 147-162.

FURLAN 2019: G. Furlan, *Dating urban classical deposits. Approaches and problems in using finds to date strata*, Oxford 2019.

GIANNATTASIO 2018: B.M. Giannattasio (ed.), *La ceramica della Sardegna meridionale. Questioni aperte e nuove prospettive*, Canterano 2018.

GHIOTTO 2004: A.R. Ghiotto, *L'architettura romana nelle città della Sardegna*, Roma 2004.

GRAHAME 1998: M. Grahame, *Redefining romanization: material culture and social continuity in Roman Britain*, in C. Forcey, J. Hawthorne & R. Witcher (eds.), *TRAC 1997, Proceedings of the Seventh Annual Theoretical Roman Archaeology Conference (Nottingham 1997)*, London, pp. 1-10.

HAEUSSLER 2016: R. Haeussler, *Becoming roman? Diverging identities and experiences in ancient northwest Italy*, Abingdon-New York 2016.

IBBA 2015: A. Ibba, *Processi di "romanizzazione" nella Sardinia repubblicana e alto imperiale (III a.C. - 2 d.C.)*, in L. Mihailescu-Bîrliiba (ed.), *Colonisation and Romanization in Moesia Inferior. Premises of a Contrastive approach*, Kaiserslautern-Mehlin 2015, pp. 11-76.

LOI 2019a: L. Loi, *Le ceramiche a vernice nera (attica, punica, campana e pasta grigia)*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 39-62, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/ar-ticle/view/3656>.

LOI 2019b: L. Loi, *Contenitori anforici di produzione punica*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 175-186, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/ar-ticle/view/3656>.

MADAU 1994: M. Madau, *Presenze puniche e romano-repubblicane in Planargia (scavi in sito Tres Bias, Tinnura-NU)*, in A. Mastino, P. Ruggeri (eds.), *L'Africa romana (Atti del X convegno di studio, Oristano 11-13 dicembre 1992)*, Sassari 1994, pp. 961-972.

MARTIN-KILCHER 1999: S. Martin-Kilcher, *Die Füllung eines frühkaiserzeitlichen Pozzo*, in *Karthago III. Die deutschen Ausgrabungen in Karthago*, Mainz, pp. 404-434.

MARTORELLI 2019: R. Martorelli (ed.), *Know the sea to live the sea. Conoscere il mare per vivere il mare*, *Atti del Convegno (Cagliari, Cittadella dei Musei – aula Coroneo, 7-9 marzo 2019)*, Borgoricco 2019.

MASTINO 2001: A. Mastino, *Rustica plebs id est in pagi in provincia Sardinia: il santuario rurale dei pagani Uneritani della Marmilla*, in S.B. Bianchetti, R. Galvagno, A. Magnelli, G. Marasco, G. Mariotta, I. Mastrarosa (eds.), *ΠΟΙΚΙΛΙΑ. Studi in onore di Michele R. Cataudella in occasione del 60° compleanno*, La Spezia 2001, pp. 781-814.

NAPOLITANO 2019: M. Napolitano, *La ceramica a pareti sottili*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 73-110, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

PAIS 1999: E. Pais, *Storia della Sardegna e della Corsica durante il periodo romano*, Nuoro 1999.

PARODO 2019: C. Parodo, *La soglia del visibile. Alcune considerazioni circa la funzione dei contenitori ceramici forati provenienti dallo scavo*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 689-716, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

PIETRA 2013: G. Pietra, *Olbia romana*, Sassari 2013.

PIETRA 2018: G. Pietra, *La villa di Tigellio. Una storia di noi*, in *Quaderni. Rivista di Archeologia* 30, 2018, pp. 179-275, <http://www.quaderniarcheocaor.beniculturali.it/index.php/quaderni/article/view/385>.

PIETRA 2019: G. Pietra, *Urbs urbium Karalis. Cagliari, la "località piazza del Carmine" in età romana*, in *Quaderni. Rivista di Archeologia* 30, 2019, pp. 143-193, <https://www.quaderniarcheocaor.beniculturali.it/index.php/qua/article/view/9/8>.

PINELLI 2019: L. Pinelli, *La ceramica comune da fuoco. Dall'età repubblicana all'Altomedioevo*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 409-452, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

PINELLI, PINELLI 2019: C. Pinelli, L. Pinelli, *La ceramica comune di età romana. Dall'età repubblicana all'Altomedioevo*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 345-388, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

PITTS 2015: M. Pitts, *Globalisation, Circulation and Mass consumption in the Roman World*, in M. Pitts, M.J. Versluys (eds.), *Globalisation and the Roman World: World history, Connectivity and Material Culture*, Cambridge 2015, pp. 69-98.

PONTIS 2018: A. Pontis, *La sigillata africana del vano A nello scavo dell'Ex Area militare (Nora – Pula)*, Università degli Studi di Cagliari (tesi), 2018.

PONTIS 2019a: A. Pontis, *La sigillata africana*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 139-168, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

PONTIS 2019b: A. Pontis, *Ceramiche da mensa dall'Africa. La sigillata D di Cagliari*, in MARTORELLI 2019, pp. 607-615.

PONTIS, D'ORLANDO 2019: A. Pontis, D. D'Orlando, *Contenitori anforici di produzione iberica*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 207-234, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

PORRÀ 2008: F. Porrà, *Karales: analisi del processo di promozione a città romana*, in *AnnCagl* 25 (62), 2007 (2008), pp. 45-69.

PORRÀ 2012: F. Porrà, *Considerazioni su Uselis, città della Sardegna romana*, in C. Del Vais (ed.), *EPI OINOPA PONTON. Studi sul Mediterraneo antico in onore di Giovanni Tore*, Oristano 2012, pp. 649-657.

PUDDU 2019: M. Puddu, *Funerary archaeology and changing identities: community practices in Roman-period Sardinia*, Oxford 2019.

ROPPA 2013: A. Roppa, *Comunità urbane e rurali nella Sardegna punica di età ellenistica*, in *Saguntum Extra-14*, Valencia 2013.

ROTH 2003: R.E. Roth, *Towards a ceramic approach to social identity in the Roman world: some theoretical considerations*, in *Digressus. The internet journal of the Classical world*, Supplement, 1, pp. 35-45.

ROTH, KELLER 2007: R. Roth, J. Keller, *Roman by integration: dimension of group identity in material culture and text*, Portsmouth 2007.

ROWLAND 1981: R.J. Rowland, *I ritrovamenti romani in Sardegna*, Roma 1981.

SANCIU 1997: A. Sanciu, *Una fattoria d'età romana nell'agro di Olbia*, Sassari 1997.

SANNA 2019: A.L. Sanna, *Intervento archeologico d'urgenza nell'area del parcheggio dell'Agenzia regionale LAORE Sardegna (Cagliari, via Caprera 8)*, in

D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 1-34, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

SORO 2019a: L. Soro, *Contenitori anforici di produzione nordafricana (I-VII secolo d.C.)*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 235-258, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

SORO 2019b: L. Soro, *Contenitori anforici di altre produzioni*, in D'ORLANDO *et alii* 2019, pp. 259-274, <http://ojs.unica.it/index.php/layers/article/view/3656>.

SPANO 1874: G. Spano, *Emendamenti ed aggiunte all'Itinerario dell'isola di Sardegna del conte Alberto della Marmora*, Cagliari 1874.

STEK 2013: T.D. Stek, *Material culture, Italic identities and the romanization of Italy*, in J. DeRose Evans (ed.), *A companion to the Archaeology of the Roman Republic*, Maiden 2013, pp. 337-353.

STIGLITZ 2017: A. Stiglitz, *Madre de Forasteros: Cagliari in età fenicia e punica*, in M. Guirguis (ed.), *From the Mediterranean to the Atlantic: people, goods and ideas between east and west (8th International Congress of Phoenician and Punic Studies, Carbonia, Sant'Antioco 21st-26th October 2013)*, in *Pholia Phoenicia. An International Journal* 1, Pisa, 2017, pp. 125-131.

TERRENATO 1998: N. Terrenato, *The romanization of Italy: Global acculturation or Cultural Bricolage?*, in C. Forcey, J. Hawthorne, R. Witcher (eds.), *TRAC 97: Proceedings of the Seventh Annual Theoretical Roman Archaeology Conference*, Nottingham 1997, Oxford 1998, pp. 20-27.

TERRENATO, RICCI 1998: N. Terrenato, G. Ricci, *I residui nella stratificazione urbana. Metodi di quantificazione e implicazioni per l'interpretazione delle sequenze: un caso di studio dalle pendici settentrionali del Palatino*, in F. Guidobaldi, C. Pavolini, P. Pergola, P.M. Barbini (eds.), *I materiali residui nello scavo archeologico. Testi preliminari e atti della tavola rotonda di Roma (16 marzo 1996)*, in *Publications de l'École française de Rome* 249, Roma 1998, pp. 89-104.

TRONCHETTI 1996a: C. Tronchetti, *La ceramica nella Sardegna romana*, Milano 1996.

TRONCHETTI 1996b: C. Tronchetti, *La machaira e la kylix: note su alcune tombe tardo-puniche da Santa Lucia di Gesico (CA)*, in *Alle soglie della classicità. Studi in onore di Sabatino Moscati*, Pisa 1996, pp. 993-1001.

TRONCHETTI 1998: C. Tronchetti, *Problemi di cronologia ceramica nella Sardegna romana*, in M.S. Balmuth, R.H. Tykot (eds.), *Sardinian and Aegean Chronology. Towards the resolution of relative and absolute dating in the Mediterranean. Proceedings of the international colloquium Sardinian Stratigraphy and Mediterranean Chronology (Tufts University, Medford, Massachusetts March 17-19 1995)*, Oxford 1998, pp. 371-382.

TRONCHETTI 2001: C. Tronchetti, *Una produzione di ceramica a vernice nera a Cagliari tra il III e il II sec. a.C.: la "Cagliari 1"*, in *Architettura, arte e artigianato nel Mediterraneo dalla Preistoria all'Alto Medioevo (Atti della Tavola Rotonda Internazionale in memoria di Giovanni Tore, Cagliari, 17-19 dicembre 1999)*, Oristano 2001, pp. 275-300.

TRONCHETTI 2003: C. Tronchetti, *Contributo alla Nora tardo antica*, in *Nora 2003*, Pisa 2003, pp. 98-103.

TRONCHETTI 2004: C. Tronchetti, *Cagliari and its Hinterland from the Archaic to the Late Roman Age*, in M. Pasquinucci, T. Weski (eds.), *Close encounters: Sea- and Riverborne Trade, Ports and Hinterlands, Ship Construction and Navigation in Antiquity, the Middle Ages and in Modern Time*, Oxford 2004, pp. 19-26.

TRONCHETTI 2008: C. Tronchetti, *Punic Sardinia in the Hellenistic Period*, in C. Sagona (ed.), *Beyond the Homeland: Markers in Phoenician Chronology*, Leven-Paris-Dudley 2008, pp. 597-629.

TRONCHETTI 2014a: C. Tronchetti, *La facies punica di Nora: la cultura materiale ceramica*, in A. Lemaire (ed.), *Phéniciens d'Orient et d'Occident. Mélanges Josette Elayi*, Paris 2014, pp. 549-555.

TRONCHETTI 2014b: C. Tronchetti, *Il problema delle imitazioni ceramiche nella Sardegna fenicia e punica. Imitazioni da originali greci e indigeni*, in R. Graellas i Fabregat, M. Krueger, S. Sardà Seuma, G. Sciortino (eds.), *El problema de las "imitaciones" durante la protohistoria en el Mediterráneo centrooccidental; entre el concepto y el ejemplo*, Madrid 2014, pp. 121-130.

TRONCHETTI 2015: C. Tronchetti, *Continuità e trasformazione nella Sardegna romana tra Repubblica e Primo Impero*, in P. Ruggeri (ed.), *L'Africa romana. Momenti di continuità e rottura: bilancio di trent'anni di convegni L'Africa romana (Atti del XX convegno Internazionale di studi, Alghero - Porto Conte Ricerche, 26-29 settembre 2013)*, Roma 2015, pp.1807-1813.

TRONCHETTI 2018: C. Tronchetti, *Aspetti e problemi della ceramica romana di Sardegna*, in GIANNATTASIO 2018, pp. 11-22.

UGAS 1993: G. Ugas, *San Sperate dalle origini ai baroni*, Cagliari 1993.

VAN DOMMELEN *et alii* 2006: P. Van Dommelen, L. Sharpe, K. McLellan, *Insediamiento rurale nella Sardegna punica: il progetto Terralba*, in A. Akerras, P. Ruggeri, A. Siraj, C. Vismara (eds.), *L'Africa romana. Mobilità delle persone e dei popoli, dinamiche migratorie, emigrazioni ed immigrazioni nelle province occidentali dell'Impero romano (Atti del XVI convegno di studio, Rabat 15.19 dicembre 2004)*, pp. 153-173.

VAN DOMMELEN 2007: P. Van Dommelen, *Beyond resistance: Roman power and local traditions in Sardinia*, in P. Van Dommelen, N. Terrenato (eds.), *Articulating local cultures: power and identity under the expanding Roman Republic*, Portsmouth 2007, pp. 55-69.

VAN DOMMELEN, TERRENATO 2007: P. Van Dommelen, N. Terrenato, *Articulating local cultures: power and identity under the expanding Roman Republic*, Portsmouth 2007.

VAN DOMMELEN *et alii* 2008: P. Van Dommelen, N. De Bruijin, H. Loney, R. Puig Moragòn, A. Roppa, *Ceramica punica dal sito rurale di Truncu 'e Molas (Terralba, Sardegna)*, in J. Gonzalez, P. Ruggeri, C. Vismara, R. Zucca (eds.), *L'Africa romana. Le ricchezze dell'Africa: risorse, produzioni, scambi (Atti del XVII convegno di studio, Sevilla 14-17 dicembre 2006)*, Roma 2008, pp.1697-1706.

VAN DOMMELEN, KNAPP 2010: P. Van Dommelen, A.B. Knapp, *Material connections in the ancient Mediterranean: mobility, materiality and Mediterranean Identities*, London/New York 2010.

VAN DOMMELEN *et alii* 2012: P. Van Dommelen, C. Gomez Bellard, C. Tronchetti, *Insediamiento rurale e produzione agraria nella Sardegna punica: la fattoria di Truncu 'e Molas (Terralba, OR)*, in C. Del Vais (ed.), *EPI OINOPA PONTON. Studi sul Mediterraneo antico in ricordo di Giovanni Tore*, Oristano 2012, pp. 501-516.

VAN OYEN 2017: A. Van Oyen, *Towards a post-colonial artefact analysis*, in *Archaeological Dialogues* 20, 1, pp. 81-107.

VAN OYEN 2017: A. Van Oyen, *Material Culture in the Romanization Debate*, in A. Lichtenberger, R. Raja (eds.), *The Diversity of Classical Archaeology*, Turnhout 2017, pp. 287-300.

ZAMPARO 2018: L. Zamparo, *La famiglia delle ceramiche a vernice nera dallo scavo del Tempio romano di Nora*, in GIANNATTASIO 2018, pp. 23-32.

ZUCCA 1994: R. Zucca, *Il decoro urbano delle civitates Sardiniae et Corsicae: il contributo delle fonti letterarie ed epigrafiche*, in A. Mastino, P. Ruggeri (eds.), *L'Africa romana (Atti del X convegno di studio, Oristano 11-13 dicembre 1992)*, Sassari 1994, pp. 857-936.

ZUCCA 1999: R. Zucca, *Cagliari. L'antichità*, in *Luoghi e tradizioni d'Italia, Sardegna*, Roma 1999, pp. 21-36.

Fig. 1. Roman Sardinia in the 1st century AD in the context of the Mediterranean Sea (picture by D. D’Orlando).

Fig. 2. The site of via Caprera 8, Cagliari. (A: House in viale Trieste 105; B: site of Palazzo Massimo; C: Mongiu excavation site 1980’s; D: Taramelli/Lilliu excavation site 1905/1950; E: Mongiu thermal baths 1980’s; F: Church of Nostra Signora del Carmine (roman road); G: Theater-temple of via Malta; H: Roman *forum* of Karales; I: Piazza Yenne excavation (roman houses) (picture by D. D’Orlando).

Fig. 3. The site of via Caprera 8 (Cagliari) during the excavation (from SANNA 2019, fig. 3).

Fig. 4. Via Caprera 8 (Cagliari). Stratigraphic section (from SANNA 2019, tav. IV).

Tab. 1. Via Caprera 8 (Cagliari). Importing trends of amphorae and fine pottery (even percentage per year of the MNI of individuals). Capital moments (I: Provincia Sardinia et Corsica; II: Third Punic war/Second conquest of the Island; III: Social war; IV: Augustan Age; V: Late I c. AD crisis (picture by D. D’Orlando).

Tab. 2. Via Caprera 8: Amphorae fragments simple percentage (picture by D. D’Orlando).

Tab. 3. Via Caprera 8. Even percentage per year on MNI of individuals of amphorae by area of production (dividing Punic and Roman African amphorae) (picture by D. D'Orlando).

Tab. 4. Via Caprera 8. Even percentage per year on MNI of individuals of amphorae by area of production (picture by D. D'Orlando).

Tab. 5. Via Caprera 8. Fine pottery fragments diagnostic percentage (picture by D. D'Orlando).

Tab. 6. Via Caprera 8. Fine pottery fragments class percentage (picture by D. D'Orlando).

Tab. 7. Via Caprera 8. Even percentage per year on MNI of individuals of fine pottery by class (picture by D. D'Orlando).

Tab. 8. Via Caprera 8. Even percentage per year on MNI of individuals of fine pottery by areas of production (picture by D. D'Orlando).

Tab. 9. Nora (Pula, CA), *forum* of the city. Even percentage per year of roman black-glazed ware (from FALEZZA 2009a, fig. 12)

Tab. 10. Via Caprera 8. Even percentage per year on MNI of individuals of amphorae and fine pottery by areas of production (picture by D. D'Orlando).